

Benefits of Using Reference Management Software

Aslam Yazid

Faculty of Information Management
Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM)
Selangor, Malaysia

Email: aslamyazid7@gmail.com

Received Date: 10 August 2021

Accepted Date: 23 August 2021

Published Date: 10 September 2021

Abstract. This paper is aim to study the benefits of using reference management software (RMS). The discussion began by focusing on the overview of RMS. The following section provides several advantages of using RMS namely, the capacity to conveniently search and import references, the capacity to construct bibliographies, the capacity to manage PDF files systematically, and offline availability.

Keywords: Reference management software, RMS, Citation manager, EndNote, Mendeley, Zotero.

Introduction

Researchers have been using reference management tools or software to organise their references since 1980 (Bertrand & Bader, 1980; Tramullas, Sánchez-Casabón, & Garrido-Picazo, 2015). Also, Bertrand and Bader (1980) state that in the 1980s, researchers had difficulty managing and classifying bibliography references, which took up a lot of time. However, Bertrand and Bader assert that the advent of computers has made it easier to access and maintain bibliographic references. Through their research, they invented a new system during that time using a microcomputer with a small microprocessor system (IMSAI) called FILOS that was able for researchers and students to create, manage and store their reference sources efficiently. In sequence, Kunin (1985) admitted applications that manage bibliographic references by using microcomputers ease the human task in the creation of citations and references. A study by Tramullas et al. (2015) explained bibliography making and word processor integration has increasingly become vital by the end of the 1990s. There is no specific definition in defining reference management software (RMS) but McMinn (2011) defined reference management software as tools that help researchers collect, organize and apply reference information effectively and efficiently this is aligned with what have stated by Rempel and Mellinger (2015) mentioned reference management

software ease researchers task in term of organizing and re-findable reference information and citation simpler to be created.

Usage Benefits

Generally, most users are aware of RMS because it is free and easy to use as reported by Speare (2018), 58% of respondents use RMS because it is free while, 62% of the respondents are interested in using RMS because it is simple to use. In detail, using RMS has several advantages regardless of whether the software is proprietary or free. Additionally, Chen et al. (2018) listed various advantages of utilising RMS, including the capacity to conveniently search and import references, the capacity to construct bibliographies, the capacity to manage PDF files systematically, and offline availability.

Searches and Importing References

One of the benefits is users can import reference files from the databases viz PubMed, Web of Science, Science Direct, EBSCO (CINAHL), and ProQuest (PsycINFO) into their RMS. Thus, to support the above statement again a study by Speare (2018) reported 59% of respondents prefer to use RMS because they can save citation files from databases like PubMed, Web of Science, EBSCOHOST and Google Scholar. What is mentioned by Speare (2018) has also been expounded by Fenner, Scheliga and Bartling (2014) that apart from inserting bibliographic entries manually which takes a long time, RMS can also import and export citations in BibTex or RIS format. With a function like this, it increases efficiency in reference management.

Alongside, Osmani et al. (2016) conducted research at a Malaysian research institution and discovered that the majority of respondents are familiar with RMS, with EndNote being the program that 92.6% of respondents are familiar with. Then, saving references (29%) and pasting references into their working page are the most commonly used features (17%).

Creation of Bibliographies

With RMS, users are able to create bibliographies and to help authors manage their references, regardless of how many they may have and maintain consistency when referencing (Amrutha, Kumar, & Kabir, 2018). Apart from that, RMS consists of automatic bibliographies generated as word processing plug-ins that allow the user to generate all the bibliography once they have cited the document (Speare, 2018). In addition, there is the latest study regarding the use of RMS traced that was published in 2020, the study findings showed a positive response from respondents who agreed by using RMS they can make citations with bibliography faster compared to manual writing (Wahyuningsih, 2020).

Plus, Basak (2015) elucidated that among the advantages of RMS is that it has a citation format according to the types of materials, particularly, books, thesis or dissertation and journal articles, where users can customize the format according to their needs. Technically, Kaur and Dhindsa (2016) revealed that there are more than 10 citation styles that can be designated by users according to different brands, Mendeley has 12 types of citation styles and Zotero which is an open-source reference management software has 16 types of citation styles. This indicates that RMS has flexibility in constructing various citation styles.

Therefore, a study by Lonergan (2017) reported feature to determine format citation is the most important component of respondents' choice.

Management of Portable Document Format Files

Most of the RMS allows users to upload PDF files easily whether through upload files or drag and drop method in the program and especially for the Mendeley program it is able to allow users to do modifications on the metadata of the file more flexible (Speare, 2018). Similarly, a positive result has shown in a study conducted by Wahyuningsih (2020) stated RMS can help users to download files easily from various databases. Next, Kali (2016) made a comparison of features found in RMS which is also equivalently discernible in a study was conducted by Kaur and Dhindsa (2016) compared that in most RMS can attach files where not everyone is aware of this function. For example, Melles and Unsworth (2015) reported that there are respondents who still use alternative techniques to store their PDF files in several storage platforms such as documentation folders, storage drives that are provided by their academic institution and there are also those who prefer to refer to the material in printed form.

Therefore, RMS not only manages citations and bibliographies, yet, also makes it easier for users to save files or documents downloaded from the database into the software according to the folder that can be created by them.

Offline Availability

A desktop version of RMS can be accessed without any internet connection except for synchronization with the web-based version will require an internet connection such as Mendeley once the user uploaded the files in the program, they can synchronize the files with the web-based version of Mendeley (Speare, 2018). Contrary, Madhusudhan (2016) focused on the evaluation of online citation tools and it is use by students in India, and the survey found that all respondents are aware of online citation tools and use them on a regular basis, with EasyBib being the most popular online citation tool among respondents. Additionally, most of the respondents learned the online citation tools through the department's website. Furthermore, the main purpose of using online citation tools was for their academic purpose or research work.

Conclusion

In summation, the main purpose of writing this article is to trace the benefits of using RMS. Based on the research that has been done, RMS has shown benefits, especially the emergence of features such as Words plug-in and PDF document management where not all users are aware and use of these features. Indeed, RMS helps researchers and students a lot in managing reference sources more easily. Especially, to generate citations and bibliographies. Undoubtedly, RMS accelerates the level of productivity among users for sorting reference documents and bibliographies in a systematically way. Although, some of them still adopt alternative methods to manage their reference sources. Herewith, future research should look at strategies to encourage the use of RMS for users who prefer to manage reference sources manually and for those who are not aware of or use RMS through experimental studies so that researchers can detect the reaction of use towards RMS before and after the learning session.

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